

REVOLUTIONIZING MURDER INVESTIGATIONS THROUGH DIGITAL FORENSICS

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ABSTRACT

The answer of this question 'How digital forensics has revolutionized murder investigations in Pakistan?' is given in this research paper. Furthermore, we come to know the role of digital forensics in homicide cases through this research paper and we have tried to explore it. That how evidences are collected, analyzed through scientific methods and technologies. The typical investigation methods face credibility challenges as the violent crimes rise; in such a cases for ensuring transparency, accuracy and timely justice the digital forensics play a vital role. Pakistan's current institutional and legal framework governing digital forensics is examined in this study, especially under the law of evidence (QSO 1984), the laws made for controlling electronic crimes (PECA 2016) and the procedural laws (CRPC). This paper points out key challenges like limited legal awareness, inadequate forensics capacity and want of coordination between forensics laboratories and law enforcement, with the help of qualitative analysis of judicial binding decisions (Precedents), reality base case studies and expert opinions. Significant strides has been made by Pakistan in establishing Punjab forensics science agency and a unit within the FIA. Findings suggest that systemic reforms and legislative enhancing remain crucial. Recommendations are provided at the end of this paper for capacity building, judicial training, legal harmonization and integration of artificial intelligence tools to strengthen Murder investigations through digital forensics in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION.

The very foundation of justice and public security is challenged by murder as it comes under one of the most heinous crimes. Investigations of this sort of crime is traditionally relied on eye witnesses , circumstantial evidence and confessions in Pakistan. As everything is advancing same is the case with the modern criminals who use technologies in accomplishing their malice aforethought, they perform such acts by using digital means. For instance mobile phone , surveillance system, social media and online communications for mapping executing and concealing their acts. Digital forensics is made indispensable component of contemporary homicide investigations by the technological advancement. The courts admit digital evidences, which are identified, collected, preserved , analyzed and presented or referred to them by digital forensics. Institution such as FIA , Punjab forensics agency (PFSA) and the response centre for cyber crimes (NRCC) in Pakistan have gradually integrated digital forensics tricks into criminal investigations.

Nevertheless the integration is hindered by legal ambiguities , limited expertise and lack of resources therefore it remained partial. The importance of this research relies in knowing that how digital forensics can revolutionized the process of murder investigations in Pakistan. Transforming them to legally defensible and scientifically grounded process from the traditional, assumption based inquiries.

The gap between technology and law is tried to be bridged with the assistance of this paper by critically analyzing , operational challenges, emerging forensics practices and the legal framework of Pakistan.

The study addresses key questions:

- How is digital forensics currently being used in Pakistan’s murder investigations?
- What legal and institutional frameworks regulate digital evidence?
- What are the primary challenges faced by investigators and prosecutors?
- How can Pakistan strengthen its digital forensic capacity to ensure effective justice delivery?

By addressing these questions, this research contributes to strengthening the integrity of Pakistan’s criminal justice system and enhancing public confidence in the rule of law.

Research Methodology

This study adopts a **doctrinal and qualitative and research approach** to examine the role of evolving of digital forensics in Pakistan’s murder investigations. Three main components involved by the methodology are :

Doctrinal Analysis

We review Existing Pakistani legislation through studies for the relevant digital forensics, including:

- The Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) 2016.
- Qanun-e-Shahadat Order (QSO) 1984 (Article 164 on electronic evidence).
- Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC).
- Pakistan Penal Code (PPC).

Judicial decisions, such as *State v. Imran Ali (2018)* (the Zainab murder case), have been analyzed to assess how the digital forensics are interpreted by the courts.

Empirical Review

Reports and operational data from the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA), Punjab Forensic Science Agency (PFSA), and National Response Centre for Cyber Crimes (NR3C) were analyzed to estimate institutional capacity and effectiveness in handling homicide investigations involving digital evidence.

Comparative Perspective

Pakistan's framework in this study with digital forensic is compared, practices in other jurisdictions such as the United Kingdom and India to identify best reforms and practices opportunities. The gathered data, academic materials, and policy documents were critically inspected to draw findings and recommendations for improving the role of digital forensics in the justice system of Pakistan.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

The Role of Digital Forensics in Murder Investigations

Digital forensics has become fundamental for uncovering the truth behind murder cases in the modern criminal justice aspect. As criminals are increasingly using electronic communication tools to map, execute, and conceal crimes, its importance has remarkably increased in Pakistan. Digital evidence such as text messages, call records, GPS data, CCTV footage, and social media interactions often provides critical links in homicide investigations that traditional methods fail to uncover.

In adopting digital forensic practices, the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) and Punjab Forensic Science Agency (PFSA) have been remained instrumental. In particular, the PFSA houses specialized units for computer forensics, mobile device analysis, and video forensics. For example, in multiple high-profile murder cases in Punjab, digital evidence recovered from CCTV cameras and mobile phones was used to detect suspects' movements and confirm their involvement.

Though, in spite such advancements, the merging of digital forensics into regular investigative procedures remains incompatible. Traditional investigation techniques are still followed heavily by the police departments due to inadequate training and want of forensic resources at the district level.

Digital Evidence and Its Admissibility in Pakistan

Digital evidence refers to any information (data), which is served to be tested, that is preserved or transmitted in digital form. Under Article 164 of the Qanun-e-Shahadat Order (QSO) 1984, courts may permit evidence generated through latest devices or techniques, provided that genuineness and reliability are established.

The Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) 2016 accompany this provision by defining the offences involving digital technology and permitting powers to preserve, investigate, and present electronic evidence. Section 29 of PECA empowers the FIA to gather, retain, and look over the data from electronic devices, provided due process is noticed.

Despite these statutory provisions, challenges remain in maintaining the data integrity and ensuring chain of custody and during forensic procedures. Due to improper documentation, absence of expert certification and unauthorized handling courts often question the authenticity of digital evidence. This need of procedural compliance compromise other strong digital evidence.

Institutional Capacity and Infrastructure

Pakistan's forensic infrastructure has grown significantly over the last decade. The Punjab Forensic Science Agency (PFSA) has become a regional model, providing thorough forensic services, including digital forensics, DNA testing and toxicology. The National Response Centre for Cyber Crimes (NRCC) under the FIA is another vital body answerable for managing digital evidence and investigating electronic crimes.

However, the capacity gap between the provincial police unit and PFSA remains considerable. Provinces such as Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Balochistan still lack fully equipped digital forensic laboratories. Moreover, law enforcement officers often go without the technical knowledge to properly gather and preserve electronic data, which leads to evidence irregularity or loss.

Due to poor handling or inadequate documentation, a report by Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (2023) shows that over 60% of criminal investigations involving digital component fail to meet admissibility standard. These integral weaknesses highlight the intense need for specialized personal, uniform training and standard operating procedures (SOPs) across all provinces.

Case Analysis: Zainab Murder Case (2018)

The prominent example of how digital forensics can revolutionize homicide investigations in Pakistan is the Zainab Ansari murder case (2018). The Punjab police, in team work with the PFSA, used CCTV footage from various cameras, cross-referenced with mobile phone location data, to track and identify the offender, Imran Ali.

This case has displayed the practical power of digital forensics in decreasing investigation time, ensuring evidence dependability, and strengthening prosecution arguments (case). The digital trail founded the basics of the prosecution's case, leading to a conviction supported by forensic evidence (Modern evidence) inset of eyewitness testimony alone.

Challenges in the Current System

Several challenges persist, despite of its successes.

Following are the obstacles:

- **Lack of Training:** Most police officials require proper education about digital evidence handling, making it difficult to ensure admissibility.
- **Inconsistent Legal Standards:** The PECA and QSO and provide general guidance but need detailed procedural rules for digital forensics.
- **Limited Infrastructure:** Among all the provinces only Punjab has a comprehensive forensic agency, while other provinces depend on old fashioned equipment or external assistance.
- **Judicial Gaps:** Judges and prosecutors often called for technical understanding, leading to underexploiting of digital evidence.
- **Privacy Concerns:** Concerns over privacy violation has been raised by the growing use of digital surveillance, necessitating strict adherence to legal safeguards.

Comparative Insights

Pakistan's combination of digital forensics into practice is still evolving as Compared to other countries like United Kingdom or India. The UK Forensic Science Regulator provides binding codes of practice that ensure the dependability of forensic results in court. Similarly, India's Central Forensic Science Laboratories (CFSLs) take good care of a national network for evidence collection and analysis. On the other hand, Pakistan's forensic system operates in silos, with confined coordination between law enforcement agencies and provincial laboratories. Establishing a National Forensic Coordination Authority could assist to unify standards, training, and technological infrastructure overall the country.

The Future of Digital Forensics in Pakistan

In Pakistan digital forensic is at an analytical turning point. The increasing generality of internet technologies and mobile means that nearly every homicide investigation involves a digital footprint. With proper reforms, in order to make the criminal justice system more transparent, efficient and scientifically credible Pakistan has to make more technological advantage or provide more power to it.

The coming out technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), data analytics, and blockchain-based evidence verification could further improve forensic reliability and efficiency if adopted within the Pakistani context.

Legal Framework Governing Digital Forensics in Pakistan

For accommodating digital evidence within the broader framework of criminal justice, Pakistan's legal system has evolved gradually. Several key statutes, judicial precedents, and institutional mechanisms shape how digital forensics works in murder investigations.

The Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) 2016

The Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) serves as the keystone of Pakistan’s cybercrime legislation. While its foremost aim is to regulate cyber offences, it also lays the foundation for handling digital evidence.

- Section 29 The Federal Investigation Agency is empowered by this section of PECA (FIA) to retain, analyze, and present digital evidence.
- Section 32 Preserving and sharing data with investigators upon lawful request is mandated by service provider as per this section.
- Section 39 Jurisdictional rules are established by this section for offences committed partly or wholly through electronic means.

Even though, PECA does not directly address homicide cases but it provides procedural authority for repossessing digital evidence—such as emails, location data and social media communications—that can construct intent or presence in murder cases.

Qanun-e-Shahadat Order (QSO) 1984

The Qanun-e-Shahadat Order, Pakistan’s foremost law of evidence, recognizes the admissibility of modern digital evidences through Article 164, which permits courts to consider any evidence produced by scientific devices. Even so, the law does not define the procedural standards for expert qualification, chain of custody or authentication. This ambiguity often makes the courts to undervalue or dismiss digital evidence, especially when the defense challenges its legitimacy.

Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC) 1898

The CrPC governs the preservation, collation and presentation of evidence in criminal cases. There are sections dealing with search, seizure, and expert testimony apply to electronic evidence, even though, it doesn’t have sections explicitly mentioning digital forensics. Amendments are required to specifically mention the seizure of digital devices and admissibility protocols.

Pakistan Penal Code (PPC)

The substantive offence of murder under Section 302 and other related provisions are defined in PPC. While it does not mention digital tools directly, digital evidence plays an important role in proving elements such as intent (mensrea ill/ bad intention) and causation.

Judicial Recognition

Pakistani courts have increasingly begun to accept digital evidence. In *State v. Imran Ali* (2018) (Zainab murder case), the Lahore High Court verify the admissibility of DNA reports and CCTV footage. Similarly, in *Muhammad Asif v. State* (2020), the court emphasized that

electronic evidence can be intensified if corroborate witness statement. These cases are the known examples of growing judicial confidence in technology-based investigations.

Challenges in Implementing Digital Forensics in Pakistan

Pakistan encounters multiple barriers in effectively utilizing digital forensics in murder investigations, despite, institutional and legislative progress such as:

1. **Lack of Specialized Training:** Due to the fact that the police and prosecutors lack the technical expertise to gather or interpret digital evidence, results in procedural errors.
2. **Weak Chain of Custody:** Because of, compromised or poorly documented evidence handling, many investigations fail.
3. **Limited Infrastructure:** As compare to Punjab the remaining other provinces like Balochistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Sindh depend on old fashioned or external facilities. While, Only Punjab possesses comprehensive forensic science agency.
4. **Judicial Knowledge Gaps:** Judges' limited comprehension of forensic procedures can lead to irregular rulings on admissibility.
5. **Privacy and Ethical Concerns:** The gathering of digital evidence from personal devices such as mobile phone, laptop and other, raises constitutional privacy issues under Article 14 (Dignity of Men) of the Constitution of Pakistan, which promises or guarantees the inviolability of privacy and dignity.
6. **Lack of Coordination:** Investigations are delayed by the absence of inter-agency collation between the FIA, Police, other law enforcement agencies and provincial laboratories.
7. **Financial and Technological Limitations:** Forensic equipment's are expensive and often outdated (old fashioned) due to port restrictions and budgetary restrictions.

Findings

Several key findings are revealed by analyzing Pakistan's current digital forensics landscape, following are the key findings:

- The accuracy of murder investigations has significantly improved by digital forensics. where applied? especially in Punjab.
- Legal provisions exist for acceptability of electronic evidence, but uniform enforcement and procedural clarity remain weak.
- Institutional disparities between provinces obstruct national standardization and timely case resolution.
- Investigative and judicial training in digital forensics is minimum, leading to underutilization of available evidence.

- Successful cases such as State v. Imran Ali (2018) exhibits that scientifically gathered digital evidence can secure convictions.
- Policy coordination between QSO, PECA and CrPC is necessary to avoid contradiction or overlapping while interpretations.

Recommendations

The following steps are recommended for transforming/ revolutionizing homicide investigations through digital forensics in Pakistan:

- **Establish a National Forensics Coordination Authority (NFCA):**
A centralized body should organize all digital forensic operations, standardization, and regulations across provinces.
- **Introduce Specialized Legislation:**
For enhancing the standards of collection, preservation, and admissibility of electronic evidence a digital evidence and forensics procedures Act ought to be enacted, which tells the methods and procedures to be followed.
- **Invest in Infrastructure and Training:**

For prosecutor, investigators, and judges the provincial forensics laboratories must be upgraded so they can work there by performing various experiments, using latest devices, they can know too much about digital forensics and degree level training program need to be developed in partnership with universities and PFSA for the sake of exchanging ideas with one another.

Judicial Education Programs:

For enhancing judges' technical understanding forensic science modules should be included in the Federal judicial Academy's curriculum. Being the guardian of constitution, the judiciary needs to be up to date as it provides justice, if judiciary lack such a knowledge it is treat to justice, causing in just decisions and it's known that "injustice anywhere is threat to justice everywhere". Therefore, the judicial education progress is very crucial.

Public-Private Collaboration:

Promote partnerships with tech firm and telecom companies for lawful cyber investigation and data sharing support under privacy safeguards.

Data Protection and Privacy:

Implement a robust Personal Data Protection Law to ensure digital investigations respect constitutional rights and citizens' privacy.

Integration of Artificial Intelligence:

For improving efficiency in murder case investigations, it's required to introduce AI tools for evidence correlation, pattern analysis and suspect profiling.

Provincial Expansion of PFSA Model:

Make departments like PFSA in Balochistan, Sindh and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa for uniform forensic capability nationwide.

CONCLUSION

Digital forensics has the ability to change murder investigations in Pakistan by providing accurate, authentic and science-based evidence that strengthens or give power to make it reliable for the criminal justice system. Reliance on traditional methods like unreliable eyewitness accounts and pressurize confessions can be reduced by the integration of investigative procedures. Though, Pakistan's progress remains uneven due to legal ambiguities, institutional weakness and technological limitations. Pakistan (Federal government) needs to adopt a holistic reform approach for entire Pakistan encompassing law making modernization, human capacity enhancement and institutional cooperation, to realize the full power of digital forensics. The success of cases like the Zainab murder have shown that when digital evidences are collected and examined scientifically, justice can be served fairly and swiftly. Therefore, digital forensics don't only enhance investigative efficiency but also hold up judicial integrity, public confidence and the rule of law—the cornerstone of a just society.

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